

Action of Dyestuffs and other Substances on Milk Dehydrogenase. Identity of Schardinger Enzyme with Xanthine Oxidase.

BY KALI PADA BASU AND SATI PRASAD MUKHERJEE.

The oxidising enzymes in milk have been the subject of intensive investigation by the Cambridge School and lately also by Wieland and his collaborators. There is a fundamental difference of opinion between the Cambridge School and Wieland with regard to these oxidising enzymes. Although Morgan, Stewart and Hopkins (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1922, **B 94**, 909) doubted that one and the same enzyme should be able to oxidise two substances of such widely different nature as xanthine and aldehydes, later observations and publications from the Cambridge School have always supported the view that one and only one enzyme is responsible for oxidising both the substances. Wieland, on the other hand, maintains that two different enzymes in milk are responsible for the oxidation of the substances of the purine group and the aldehydes. The experimental evidences from the two laboratories might be briefly discussed.

Dixon and Thurlow (*Biochem. J.*, 1924, **18**, 976) were unable by any means to effect a separation of the enzymes and found by comparing a large number of enzyme preparations from different milks, a striking parallelism between the two activities. The p_H curves of the two reactions were found to be very similar. Uric acid was found to inhibit both the aldehyde and the xanthine oxidation in the similar manner. Wieland and Rosenfeld (*Annalen*, 1930, **77**, 32) found that the ratio between the xanthine oxidation capacity and salicylaldehyde oxidation capacity increased on keeping and more quickly on shaking the milk (Wieland and Macrae, *Annalen*, 1930, **488**, 217). The power of milk to oxidise xanthine gradually increased, whereas the power to oxidise aldehyde practically remained constant. Dixon and Thurlow explained this as being due to the accelerating effect of fat on xanthine oxidation only. Wieland and Rosenfeld could also alter the ratio of X-E—Sa-E to about ten times by subjecting the enzyme materials to adsorption.

However, Wieland and Macrae measured the time of decolourisation of a given quantity of methylene blue by milk enzyme separately by xanthine and by salicylaldehyde and also in the presence of both the substrates. Contrary to their expectations they did not find a diminution in the time for decolourisation of the dyestuff in presence of the two substrates although both were present in optimum concentration.

Sen (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, **25**, 855) measured the absorption of oxygen by the combined system of hypoxanthine and vanillin in presence of milk enzyme and observed a somewhat less adsorption than with the more active substrate alone and attributed this to the existence of one enzyme only. Wieland and Mitchell (*Annalen*, 1932, **492**, 156) are of opinion that this might be caused by the mutual inhibitory effect of the two substrates on their adsorption on the enzyme surface. But they also failed to observe any decrease in the time of decolourisation of methylene blue by xanthine by the addition of increasing amounts of acetaldehyde.

They also thought that with quinone as the acceptor the dehydrogenation proceeded a bit more quickly in vessels containing the mixture of the two substrates than in vessels containing only one substrate. It must be remarked, however, that this summation effect is not very pronounced from their data. After the manuscript was ready another paper by Booth (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, **29**, 1732) has appeared from the Cambridge laboratory in which the identity of the two enzymes is again emphasised. Thus the whole question of the identity of the two enzymes responsible for the oxidation of purine bases and aldehydes is still open and requires further investigation.

Toxic actions of substances of known structure on an enzyme would give us some information about the nature of the active group in the latter. Investigations in this line were carried out by Bamann and Schemmler (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1931, **194**, 1) who showed that indicators of the type phenolphthalein, bromothymol blue, etc., have a toxic action on lipase. Quastel (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, **25**, 628, 898; 1932, **26**, 1685) has tried the action of a series of acidic and basic dyes on dehydrogenase, fumarase and urease, and recently Basu and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 82) tried the action of various dyestuffs on proteolytic enzymes, *e.g.*, trypsin and papain. It should be possible to distinguish between apparently closely related enzymes like the different proteinases, polypeptidases, etc., by taking advantages of the specific toxic action of the dyestuffs.

The present investigation was, therefore, carried out to determine the action of a series of dyestuffs, some narcotics and certain other substances on the oxidation of xanthine and of aldehydes by milk dehydrogenase in order to find out the nature of the active group in the enzyme and also to see whether any of the investigated dyestuffs and other substances revealed any difference in behaviour towards the oxidation of these substances. It should be possible by this means to establish the identity or other wise of the Schardinger enzyme with the xanthine oxidase.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The caseinogen preparation obtained by the method of Dixon and Thurlow (*loc. cit.*) was employed as enzyme material. Attempts to prepare the cream preparation by the method of Wieland and Rosenfeld (*loc. cit. cf. also Toyama, Biochem. J. Japan, 1933, 17, 131*) did not give satisfactory results. The enzyme material was preserved in the refrigerator. Absorption measurements were carried out in Barcroft-Warburg respirometers at 37°.

Determination of Optimum p_H and Optimum Concentration of the Substrate.

Using hypoxanthine and aldehydes, Dixon and Thurlow (*loc. cit.*) determined the optimum p_H and optimum concentration of the substrates with methylene blue as the hydrogen acceptor. So far as the oxidation in oxygen is concerned, very little data is available with regard to the optimum p_H and optimum substrate concentration.

Optimum p_H .—Using xanthine, salicylaldehyde and acetaldehyde with same concentration of the enzyme solution and phosphate buffer the following variation of their oxygen uptake was noted with the change of p_H .

TABLE I a.

Substrate—xanthine. 4 C.c. of 3% caseinogen enzyme preparation solution in water brought to desired p_H , 2 c.c. of $M/300$ -xanthine solution at desired p_H and 2 c.c. of phosphate buffer ($M/3$) used.

	Oxygen absorption in c.c. at p_H				
Time.	5.2	6.2	7.1	8.0	9.1
15 min.	0.0157	0.0248	0.0388	0.0482	0.0423
30	0.0216	0.0362	0.0469	0.0603	0.050
60	0.0216	0.0392	0.050	0.0661	0.0560

TABLE Ib.

Substrate—salicylaldehyde. 4 C.c. of 3% enzyme solution, 2 c.c. of $M/100$ -salicylaldehyde at desired p_H and 2 c.c. of phosphate buffer used.

Time.	Oxygen absorption in c.c. at p_H				
	5·2	6·2	7·1	8·0	9·1
15 min.	0·010	0·010	0·0212	0·0241	0·0267
30	0·0143	0·0162	0·0299	0·0372	0·0362
60	0·0162	0·0196	0·0352	0·0421	0·0412

TABLE Ic.

Substrate—acetaldehyde. 4 C.c. of enzyme solution, 2 c.c. of $M/5$ -acetaldehyde at desired p_H and 2 c.c. of phosphate buffer used.

Time	Oxygen absorption in c.c. at p_H				
	5·2	6·2	7·1	8·0	9·1
15 min.	0·0072	0·020	0·0231	0·0311	0·0298
30	0·0126	0·0271	0·0312	0·0412	0·0401
60	0·0126	0·0312	0·0346	0·0445	0·0445

Thus the optimum p_H for the action of milk dehydrogenase using xanthine, salicylaldehyde and acetaldehyde as substrates and molecular oxygen as hydrogen acceptor, has been found to be 8·0. With methylene blue as hydrogen acceptor, Wieland and Rosenfeld obtained p_H 8 as the optimum p_H for the oxidation of xanthine and salicylaldehyde, while Dixon and Thurlow with methylene blue and hypoxanthine found that the reaction velocity was not affected between p_H 5·5 and 9.

Optimum Substrate Concentration.—Using xanthine, salicylaldehyde and acetaldehyde at optimum p_H (*i.e.*, p_H 8·0) with the same concentration of the enzyme solution and phosphate buffer, the following variation of oxygen uptake was noted with the variation of substrate concentration.

TABLE IIa.

Substrate—xanthine. 4 C.c. of 3% enzyme solution at p_n 8.0, 2 c.c. of substrate at p_n 8.0 and 2 c.c. of phosphate buffer used.

Time.	Oxygen uptake with substrate conc. of			
	M/400.	M/800.	M/1200.	M/1600.
15 min.	0.0147 c.c.	0.0157 c.c.	0.0514 c.c.	0.0405 c.c.
30	0.0249	0.0264	0.0642	0.050
60	0.0264	0.0302	0.0690	0.0535

TABLE IIb

Substrate—salicylaldehyde. 4 C.c. of 3% enzyme solution at p_n 8.0; 2 c.c. of substrate at p_n 8.0 and 2 c.c. of phosphate buffer used.

Time.	Oxygen uptake with substrate conc. of			
	M/100.	M/200.	M/400.	M/600.
15 min.	0.010 c.c.	0.0172 c.c.	0.0256 c.c.	0.0251 c.c.
30	0.0162	0.020	0.0360	0.0351
60	0.0219	0.0236	0.0402	0.0382

TABLE IIc.

Substrate—acetaldehyde. 4 C.c. of 3% enzyme solution at p_n 8.0; 2 c.c. of substrate at p_n 8.0 and 2 c.c. of phosphate buffer used.

Time.	Oxygen uptake with substrate conc. of			
	M/6.	M/10.	M/20.	M/30.
15 min	0.0092 c.c.	0.0132 c.c.	0.030 c.c.	0.0210 c.c.
30	0.0176	0.020	0.0395	0.0331
60	0.020	0.023	0.0436	0.0360

It will be evident from the above that the optimum p_n and using 4 c.c. of 3% enzyme solution at requisite p_n in a total volume of 8 c.c. of the reaction mixture, the followings are the optimum substrate concentrations.

Xanthine, M/1200; salicylaldehyde, M/400; acetaldehyde, M/20.

Experiments with Dyestuffs.

The effect of the dyestuffs on the oxidation of the substrates, xanthine, salicylaldehyde, and acetaldehyde was observed under optimum conditions. The method was to determine the amount of

oxygen absorbed in certain periods by the enzyme, the substrate, and buffer under optimum conditions and the same by the substrate, buffer and the enzyme which has already been subjected to the action of various dyestuffs for half an hour. Comparing the absorption of oxygen in both cases, the amount of inhibition produced by the dyestuffs could be calculated.

In the case of the action of the dyestuffs, 4 c.c. of 3% enzyme solution at p_H 8.0, 1 c.c. of $M/3$ -phosphate buffer and 1 c.c. of $1/750$ dye solution were placed in the Barcroft vessel. The concentration of the dye in the vessel was now $1/4500$. The vessel was then allowed to stay for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour in the thermostat at 37° so as to subject the enzyme to the action of dyestuff. After this period 2 c.c. of the substrate at optimum concentration and previously brought to p_H 8.0 and to 37° , were added quickly to the vessel and thus the volume was made up to 8 c.c. The concentration of the dye was now $1/6000$ in the reaction mixture. The vessel was then shaken. Duplicate estimations were carried out in every case and the mean results were taken.

The action of a large number of acidic and basic dyestuffs from different series, *e.g.*, triphenylmethane, monoazo, tetraazo, diphenylmethane, pyronine, thiazine, safranines, the eurhodines and also hæmatoxylin were tried. The results obtained are summarised in the following table.

TABLE III

Mean percentage of inhibition.

Acidic Dyestuffs				Basic Dyestuffs			
	Xan- thine.	Acetal- dehyde	Salicylal- dehyde		Xan- thine.	Acetal- dehyde	Salicylal- dehyde
Hæmatoxylin	Nil	Nil	Nil	Janus green	26.6	21.2	19.2
Erythrosin	39.5	41.9	39.4	Ethyl violet	62	54.1	48.3
Soluble blue	2	Nil	Nil	Methyl violet	22.9	21.9	11.9
Eosin yellow	Nil	Nil	Nil	Methylene violet	20.1	21.6	18.4
Fosin bluish	2.7	Nil	5.2	Gentian violet	38.9	29.9	21.2
Acid green	Nil	Nil	Nil	Crystal violet	27	55.7	46.8
Orange-G	22.3	20.9	22.2	Bismarck brown	62.5	60	57.4
Neutral red	Nil	4.7	6.9	Safranin	34.2	21.5	22.1
Congo red	Nil	1.9	5.2	Pyronine	Nil	1.9	Nil
Benzopurpurine	1.5	2.7	Nil	Auramin	34.9	37.9	38.2
Water blue	Nil	3.9	Nil	Toluidine blue	73.8	75.7	75.8
Acid fuchsin	1.5	Nil	Nil	Brilliant green	9.1	6.7	6.8
				Chrysoidine	Nil	2.0	Nil
				Malachite green	17.4	14.3	15.9

It will be seen from the above results that all the dyestuffs behave exactly similar towards xanthine and aldehyde oxidation by the milk enzyme. Considering the results as a whole, the acidic dyestuffs with the exception of erythroisin and orange-G, are without any effect on the oxidation of the xanthine and the aldehydes and the two acidic dyestuffs, erythroisin, and orange-G, inhibit both xanthine and aldehyde oxidation to the same extent. All the basic dyestuffs with the exception of pyronine and chrysoidine exert a pronounced and equal inhibitory effect on the oxidation of xanthine as well as of aldehydes. This action of all the dyestuffs, without any exception, make it almost certain that in milk, one and only one oxidising enzyme causes the oxidation of purine bases and aldehydes. The active group in the enzyme appears to be acidic in nature.

Experiments with Narcotics.

In order to see if narcotics and certain other substances affected the oxidation of purine bases and of the aldehydes in a different manner, the effect of four narcotics, *e.g.*, diethylurea, ethylurethane, phenylurethane and phenylurea, as well as of the following substances: *viz.*, pyrogallol, sodium hydrosulphite and gallic acid, was determined in a manner exactly similar to that for determining the effect of dyestuffs. The experimental results are given in the following table.

TABLE IV.

Percentage inhibition.

Substrates →	Xanthine.	Salicylaldehyde.	Acetaldehyde.
<i>Narcotics.</i>			
Diethylurea	1.9	2	3.8
Ethylurethane	1.7	0	0
Phenylurethane	1.6	5.6	5
Phenylurea	0	0	0
<i>Other substances.</i>			
Pyrogallol	24.1	20.1	26.3
Sodium hydrosulphite	1.9	3.9	1.2
Gallic acid	11.4	7	12.2

It will be found that the four narcotics are almost without any effect on the oxidation of xanthine as well as of the two aldehydes.

Similar results were obtained by Sen (*loc. cit.*). This observation runs contrary to the views of Keilin on oxidation who holds that narcotics have no action on the activity of the oxidisable system but inhibit the activity of the dehydrogenation system. Of the three substances pyrogallol, sodium hydrosulphite and gallic acid, pyrogallol has got a pronounced but same inhibitory effect on both oxidations. Sodium hydrosulphite is without any effect, while gallic acid exerts a slight inhibitory action on both the oxidations.

All these observations point to the identity of the Schardinger enzyme with the xanthine oxidase.

SUMMARY.

1. Using the caseinogen preparation of Dixon and Thurlow with air as the hydrogen acceptor, the optimum p_H and the optimum substrate concentration of xanthine, salicylaldehyde and acetaldehyde oxidations have been determined.

2. The actions of various acidic and basic dyestuffs, from different series, on the oxidation of xanthine, salicylaldehyde and acetaldehyde by the milk enzyme, have been determined under optimum conditions.

3. It has been found that the acidic dyestuffs with the exception of erythrosin and orange-G are without any effect on the oxidation of the xanthine and the aldehydes. All the basic dyestuffs with the exception of pyromine and the chrysoidine exert a pronounced and equal inhibitory effect on the oxidation of xanthine as well as of aldehydes. The active group in the enzyme appears to be acidic.

4. The action of four narcotics and three other substances has been observed on the same oxidation systems and it has been found that the narcotics are without any effect on the oxidation of both purine base and aldehydes. Of the three other substances, pyrogallol has got a pronounced but same inhibitory effect on both oxidations. Sodium hydrosulphite is without any effect, while gallic acid exerts a slight inhibitory action on both the oxidations.

5. All these observations point to the identity of the Schardinger enzyme with the xanthine oxidase.

Our thanks are due to Prof. J. C. Ghosh for his interest in our work.